

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (VERSION 2.0)

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Key deliverable information

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Project coordination and scientific lead team	Ilkhom Soliev; Alex Franklin; Agnes Zolyomi; Torsten Wähler

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Corresponding author	Alex Franklin
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Executive Summary

Alarming and continued loss of biodiversity now threatens both the biosphere and human life through failures in fundamental ecosystem service delivery. System-wide transformative changes are needed, including altering paradigms, behaviour and values (IPBES, 2019). To address this, PLANET4B provides insight into the diverse perceptions of biodiversity and its communication to understand behaviours and motivations around biodiversity prioritisation. Existing multidisciplinary behaviour theories (e.g. framing, nudging, leverage points) that could be applied for biodiversity decision-making are explored. Factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability are being reviewed to understand how they can potentially impact biodiversity perception and decision making. Founded on this knowledge, a transdisciplinary framework is being developed for changing attitudes and behaviour in a generative way, which actively embraces the transformative power of plural knowledges and intersectional diversity. Relevant behaviour change (e.g. experiential games), creative and deliberative (e.g. story-telling) methods are being adapted and applied in 11 place-based and sectoral cases from 8 countries, EU and at global level to explore the applicability of these theories and methods for triggering transformative change. Having monitored the impacts of these co-creative and participatory interventions in a range of key sectors, as well as socio-cultural and environmental settings, the findings will be synthesised and scaled up to EU and global levels to serve as inputs for EU and international policies (e.g. implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, post-2020 global biodiversity framework) and for businesses about how transformative change can be triggered. Target groups, sectors and institutions will be enabled with the gained knowledge and methods to initiate transformative change.

1 Introduction

This Data Management Plan (DMP) explains how the PLANET4B project secures and manages data and how it complies with data management policies including the FAIR principles and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The DMP defines guidelines for all consortium members, inclusive of all individuals who have access to, manage and use the project data, on how to handle various types of data sensitivity and data security.

This version (V2.0) of the PLANET4B DMP is the second of three scheduled iterations to be produced during the active life-time of the project. It will be replaced by a third (final) version (3.0/Deliverable 6.3) in month 36 of the project.

By implementing a staged approach to the planning and management of PLANET4B data throughout the lifetime of the project, we are able to ensure that we remain responsive to and up-to-date with any changes in methodological strategy at both the individual case study and overall project level. This precautionary approach is important given the participatory (action orientated) and generative approach that forms the basis of PLANET4B.

This DMP is primarily concerned with the management of data for research purpose. In the case of data collected and stored – via the PLANET4B website – for the purpose of communicating research findings (and/or any associated ‘ask the expert’ online interaction with data subjects), this is governed by a separate data privacy policy, a copy of which is included as an Annex to this document.

In the remainder of this document, firstly a data summary is provided, followed by sections on the FAIR Data Management principles and implications of the project, data security and ethical aspects as well as the GDPR principles integration to the project. The document concludes with an Annex containing corresponding individual case study level DMPs (Annex 1), template ‘Participant Information’ and ‘Informed Consent’ forms (Annex 2) and a copy of the PLANET4B website privacy policy (Annex 3).

2 Data Summary

The purpose of the data collection and its relation to the objectives of the PLANET4B project is to provide insight into the diverse perceptions of biodiversity and its communication to understand behaviours and motivations around biodiversity prioritisation. The data collection is required in order to understand 1) how factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability, norms, values and behaviour intersect and are implicated in biodiversity relevant decision-making across a range of different scales and settings; and in turn, 2) how best to channel this understanding of complexity into the design of stakeholder interventions, transformative pathways and a series of targeted (yet, scalable) policy recommendations, in order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss.

The data collection is centred around adapting and applying relevant behaviour change, creative and deliberative methods in 11 intensive/place-based and extensive/sectoral cases from 8 countries, EU and at global level to explore the applicability of these theories and methods for triggering transformative change. This activity is complimented by the use of a mix of more traditional desk- and field-based social science methods alongside, including for the purposes of measuring the impact of any interventions undertaken.

PLANET4B involves both primary and secondary data collection. The project commenced with desk-based secondary data collection (e.g. literature reviews) and also consortium partner workshops (Work Packages 1, 2 and 3). As an integral part of this first stage (particularly months 1–9) consortium partners were also asked to make known to Task leaders any existing data sets which have relevance to the project (including, if applicable, reducing the requirement for primary data collection in instances where the required data/information already exists). In relation to the primary data collection associated with the 11 case studies, exact data collection methods are by now largely agreed upon (for further detail on data collection methods per case study see Annex 1). However, in accordance with the action research orientated nature of the PLANET4B case study work, it is still possible that some anticipated future methods to be used and/or types of data to be collected may still evolve during the course of the next 6–12 months.

In the case of the intensive place-based case studies, in addition to standard social science research methods (e.g. interviews, focus groups, survey) all feature at least

one form of generative intervention method and potentially a combination of more than one type (e.g. behavioural nudge, 'serious game', creative, arts based). Depending on the outcomes and learning gained from the application of the intervention methods within individual case study settings, refined versions will also then be used to support the project's scaling up and scaling out activities with key national and international stakeholders (Work Package 4).

Overall then, the format of the data varies in size and attribute. It includes data such as original tangible data (video (.mp4) and audio recordings (.mp3), hard copy surveys, field notes, signed consent forms (.doc, .pdf), drawings (.jpg), etc.), digital data (e.g. interview schedules, workshop design, transcribed interviews and focus group discussions (.docx, .pdf), photographic (.tif) or video recordings (.mp4)), and processed data sets used in publications, including information to understand the processing (e.g. coding steps, data (.doc, .xls) to allow others to check and/or replicate the process leading to the results, and to guarantee transparency and scientific integrity of data processing.

PLANET4B research involves human participants as 'volunteers for social or human sciences research'. The involvement of human participants refers to their role as respondents, and upon occasion as participatory action research collaborators – during individual case study interventions especially (WP3). All such involvement is subject to detailed ethical standards (please see the Ethics section of this DMP; 'Part 4: Ethics Self-Assessment' of the Grant Agreement; also Articles 14 and 15 of the Grant Agreement for further details).

Ethical issues primarily relate to the involvement of research participants, including members of the public from minority groups and the youth. Emphasis will be placed on engagement of individuals representing (in total) a wide range of social characteristics (e.g. gender, age, ethnicity, religion, disability) in accordance with the call's prioritisation of intersectionality. Data collected may include sensitive personal data (e.g. race or ethnic origin, religious beliefs, political opinion, health).

Interventions are being designed for the purpose of achieving the impact of encouraging greater understanding, support and action towards prioritisation of biodiversity. There will be no negative or adverse impacts (social, environmental, economic, political or cultural) resulting from research participation in this project, or from the research activities more broadly.

3 FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

PLANET4B will make data open whenever possible, but as closed as necessary when taking into consideration personal data and privacy. When affecting confidentiality and privacy, data will not be shared publicly. In all other cases, we aim to make the research data as widely available as possible, considering the FAIR principles.

Regarding metadata and data findability, based on data collection completed to date and/or planned in the coming months, it is anticipated that:

- Where primary data are recorded in written form and are suitable for open access sharing (i.e. in full accordance with GDPR, without identifying individual research respondents in cases where anonymity forms a condition of consent for their participation, or with the consent of the research participant) it will be made available for uploading into a digital repository.
- All data uploaded into a digital repository will be accompanied by descriptive and administrative metadata. A common template will be designed and included in V3.0 (month 36) in accordance with the FAIR principle of 'making data findable', and will be used by all consortium partners. The metadata will include information such as the title of the case study, the names of participating consortium partners, an abstract, basic information on methodology using controlled vocabulary (e.g. kind of data, key words, country of data collection, category of respondents, sampling procedure, method of data collection and data collection period).
- In the case that a data entry has to be 'cleaned' to ensure respondent anonymity, this will be noted as part of the corresponding descriptive meta data.
- The data collected by the PLANET4B partners will include a mixture of both qualitative and quantitative data. It will also include a mixture of both primary and secondary data. In cases where secondary data is publicly accessible the repository will include information on the source in order that it can be accessed directly.
- To comply with GDPR, unless respondents specifically request that their names, and/or any other personal data be included in the publication of research results, personal data such as names will either be replaced by a pseudonym or unique reference code. Master files detailing the individual respondents to which the pseudonym or codes relate will be password protected and securely stored. Access to these files will be limited to the consortium partners directly involved with data collection in relation to that individual activity or case.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

With the consent of the research participant, and with the exclusion of data to be treated as secure data not for sharing – i.e. namely data affected by GDPR (esp. personal data and 'special categories of personal data' (formally known as 'sensitive data')), and/or raising any ethical concerns, data will ultimately be shared on an open access basis. The only exception to this will be audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions. In the case of these data types, where full pseudonymisation is not possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent) they will not be shared via open access.

Open access data sharing will be instigated in accordance with a period of embargo – by/before October 31st, 2025 – during which access to the data will first be restricted to the consortium partners of PLANET4B. Once the embargo period has expired in PLANET4B, open access data will be deposited in secure open access repositories (e.g. authorised secure institutional or national level data repositories) in accordance with the existing (GDPR compliant) regulations of the host (partner) institutions and in accordance with the PLANET4B DMP.

In all cases, the data will be hosted on secure servers, fulfilling EU regulations on data protection. The repository systems to be used will be selected on the basis they do not require any specific software and provide open access according to UK, Swiss, Norwegian and EU regulation (as applicable).

For ease of access, and to identify which data sets are stored in the PLANET4B repository/ies, metadata will be provided on the PLANET4B website, with (wherever possible) direct hyperlinks to the location of storage. Similarly, publications based on data collected within PLANET4B will be listed on the website, with a hyperlink to full-text on the website of the journal (all publications will be open-access compliant). The PLANET4B project website will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after the completion of PLANET4B (i.e. at least until October 2030), ensuring access to the data and the visibility of the publications.

In accordance with the Grant Agreement contractual obligations of PLANET4B, all research related data (excluding personal and ‘special categories of personal data’ (formally known as ‘sensitive data’) (see below)) will be stored for five years after the end of the research project (in case there is a high interest in the datasets or due to different national legislation, data may be stored for a longer period, which will be transparently discussed and approved within the consortium and relevant parties). Data that are used for publication will be stored for a minimum of five years after publication.

In the case of personal data and ‘special categories of personal data’, this will be destroyed within six months of the end of the research project. It is necessary to retain such data until this point in accordance with the right of research participants to withdraw their data from the study at any time until the end of the project (see also Annex 2).

For the vast majority of the data sets uploaded to the open access repository(ies), no specialist software packages will be required beyond those included in standard operating systems. Apart from general data formats of e.g. Microsoft Office; Adobe Reader; video playing and photo screening general software, open source GIS software such as QGIS, the data may also be saved in formats suitable for long-term accessibility (e.g. RTF, TXT, ZIP, XML, CSV, SHP, DBF, GeoTIFF, NetCDF, MOV, MPEG, AVI, MP3, WAVE, ASCII, DTA, POR, SAS, SAV, PDF, WARC).

During the 2022 kick-off meeting of the PLANET4B it was re-confirmed that a PLANET4B Ethics Committee (P4B-EC) would be established by month three of the project and that Data Management would be included within the responsibilities of the P4B-EC. The P4B-EC consists of representatives from CU (Alex Franklin), IFZ (Sandra Karner) and FiBL (Robert Home). It held its first meeting on March 30th, 2023, with the key points of that meeting reported back to the WP Leads and Steering Committee and has since been meeting on a six-monthly basis.

3.3 Making data interoperable

PLANET4B will use controlled vocabularies (DDI, CESSDA, European Social Science Thesaurus) in the metadata to allow interoperability. Using controlled vocabularies to describe the methodology used to collect the data, analytical and procedural

information, definitions of variables, units of measurement, will help the data to be discovered and reused.

Data produced through PLANET4B (e.g. inclusive of unstructured and semi-structured only data types (e.g. creative workshops, story-telling, semi or unstructured (narrative) interviews, participant observation accounts, photographs, videos, drawings, numeric data)) will use standard formats (e.g. .docx, .pdf, .txt, .jpeg, .avi formats), as much as possible being compliant with available (open) software applications, facilitating also recombination with various datasets from different origins, and will be uploaded onto the PLANET4B repositories in file types supportive of interoperability.

3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

Whenever suitable, data will be Open Access licensed data after careful consideration of personal data, Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements. Based on Open Access regulation, we allow data to be re-used by third parties, but with restrictions if IPR or other rights demand such restriction. Data licensing is based on guidance provided by the co-ordinating team (MLU/CU). Copyright of the data, if applicable, will be based on the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) and EU guidance; IPR ownership will be based on the Consortium Agreement. Restrictions on sharing data may apply in case of protecting propriety or patentable data (although no such instance is envisaged).

Prior to being made accessible the data will be reviewed and cleared by the directly associated consortium partner(s) (i.e. those responsible for the original collection of such data). The quality of the metadata will also be checked by the P4B-EC. Where necessary, additional external expert advice (e.g. from institutional or national GDPR and data management experts) will also be secured. Where relevant, access to the data will be dependent on any agreed embargo period. In the case of raw and processed data generated through the course of the case study component of PLANET4B, this will be made available during the final 3 months (months 33–36) of the project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, generation of the necessary metadata and, in accordance with the rights of research participants, withdrawal from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

All anonymised/pseudonymised data will be stored at least for five years after the end of the research project. There is no time limit for its re-usability because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data . that, even when it becomes 'outdated', will retain potential value in perpetuity as historical data. In case of sharing data or restricting certain data with third parties outside of the consortium, a data sharing agreement will be set up that will also detail participant consent for data sharing, copyright permissions, and agreement on any embargo period. Data sharing will be limited to anonymised processed data only, with no raw data shared. Data will be used in standard forms allowing reuse, as well as allowing searchability.

Data quality assurance processes will be undertaken, including applied standards and methodologies based on the DCC guidance. The collection and processing of data in the case of all 11 individual PLANET4B case studies is being conducted in conformity with this overarching DMP.

3.5 Allocation of resources

Any legitimate costs for making data FAIR and ensuring Open Access especially for publications based on the data collected will be covered from the existing PLANET4B consortium partner budgets. A task of the P4B-EC is to advise the Steering Committee on an amount to be reserved by consortium partners for any newly arising costs associated with FAIR compliance.

The coordinator and the consortium partners will ensure that their specific nominated repository will store relevant data in a safe place, and that specific expertise is provided for managing and updating such portals. Where host institution repositories are used the costs for ongoing maintenance of the repositories themselves will be met by the host institutions.

This DMP applies to all researchers of the PLANET4B consortium, and individually each consortium partner will be responsible for managing their data adequately. The main responsibility for correct data management lies with each individual staff member in accordance with the PLANET4B DMP and guidance provided by the host institution. The consortium partner institution of the researcher/staff member is formally responsible for all data gathered during the employment contract. If the employment contract of an individual research ends, they will be responsible for leaving datasets that have been gathered as part of the employment activities in an accessible way and in compliance with this DMP, the policy of the host partner institution and with any other relevant legal requirements.

If PLANET4B researchers publish with co-authors outside PLANET4B, in instances where this involves access to data sets, they will ensure that the external co-authors have read the PLANET4B DMP, including full compliance with GDPR regulation. In the case of authors from third party institutions sharing of GDPR sensitive data will be limited to anonymised processed data only, with no raw data shared in which it is possible to identify respondents.

Although a PLANET4B Ethics Committee has been established to oversee the delivery of the DMP, ultimately responsibility for data management is a joint individual and collective responsibility of all individuals directly involved in PLANET4B research, and all partner institutions. The P4B-EC regularly reports to and provides recommendations to the Steering Committee and individual partners.

4 Data security

4.1 Data to be stored

The aim is to ensure that data sets and records provide sufficient information to external parties to establish the scientific integrity of the information and that the scientific outcomes are reliably based on the evidence collected by researchers. The following data will and/or is envisaged to be stored:

- Original tangible data, e.g. hard copy of surveys, signed informed consent forms
- Raw digital data, e.g. audio or video recordings, transcripts of interviews or workshops, drawings, photographs, etc.

- Processed data sets used in publications, including information to understand the processing, in particular:
 - i) Coding steps;
 - ii) Data cleaning logs;
 - iii) Sufficient metadata to allow others to check and/or replicate the process leading to the results.
- Data used in publications. This includes:
 - i) Sample copies of records used to collect information (e.g. interview schedules, questionnaires, fieldwork notes if used in a publication, drawings, photographs, videos and films, etc.);
 - ii) Analysed research data (such as datasets held in databases, spreadsheets, midterm reports);
 - iii) Supporting documents (date of the collected information, source of the information, place, etc.).
- Intermediate data sets (where necessary) to guarantee transparency and scientific integrity of data processing
- Data required by involved partners/funding agencies. This includes:
 - i) Recording of procedures (protocol documents, application for regularly approvals and approvals granted, risk assessments). Records relating to the financial management of the project (invoices, orders, delivery note, supporting account records, etc.).
- Any data sharing agreements

4.2 Data storage

Tangible data and paper records are kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team.

Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases is password protected. Passwords are only known by authorised individuals. Access controls are regularly reviewed and updated as individuals join or leave the project. Computers and software are not left logged in and unattended. Digital data is stored in the format in which they have been generated.

Where data are stored in folders on the institutional networked shared drive, appropriate access control is implemented to restrict access to data and records to authorised individuals.

A project-specific shared drive has been set up (Microsoft Teams channel, hosted by CU) where access is limited to authorised individuals with password and multi-factor authentication. This shared drive is not used for storage and sharing of raw field data, rather sharing is limited to processed and secondary field data only.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, including computer hard disks, consideration is given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. Small media devices such as USB sticks and CDs are not considered suitable as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information. When they are used to transport data they will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data, a large dataset relating to 1000 or more individuals, or data that would cause

significant harm or distress to somebody if released. In addition, as the data will need to be kept for a long period (min. 5 years), consideration will be given to the expected lifespan of the storage media used as media degradation and technological advances may make the records stored on it inaccessible in the future (with advice also sought from any in-house Digital Services support of consortium partner Institutions (where applicable)).

As the storage of research records through the use of cloud computing offered by private service providers such as Apple, Google, Amazon, etc. can carry significant governance and management risks, their use is not advised, unless doing so is a requirement of the host partner institution.

To store records, PLANET4B partners have been advised to use a folder structure based on the functions and activities of their individual tasks. This will make it easier to share information with other authorised personnel.

4.3 Accessibility

Privacy and confidentiality of data is guaranteed at all times, in line with legal requirements, consortium partner institution policy and best practice.

Raw data is only be available to the researchers directly involved in the associated case study and task. Access by third parties has to be negotiated with the project coordinator or directly associated consortium partner unless otherwise specified.

Should ethical questions or concerns about the integrity of research data or data management be raised, access to data will be granted in line with legal requirements, partner institutional policy and guidance, and, where applicable, European Commission policy. Established guidelines for academic good practice, as for example provided by academic associations or research councils, will be consulted where appropriate.

5 Ethical aspects

5.1 Overview

The PLANET4B consortium is committed to ethical research and to the **principles** described in the [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union](#), the [European Convention on Human Rights](#) and its supplementary [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union in Practice](#) and will abide by the spirit of pioneering documents (such as the Nuremberg Code and the Declaration of Helsinki) and will carry out its activities according to standard procedures as advised by the European Commission.

To safeguard the overall implementation of the respective ethical standards and support in addressing new ethical issues that might arise in the course of the programme, PLANET4B has established an **Ethics Committee (P4B-EC)**. It consists of representatives from CU (Alex Franklin), IFZ (Sandra Karner) and FiBL (Robert Home). All members have extensive ethical expertise. In addition to overseeing consortium compliance with Research Ethics, the P4B-EC also takes the lead in ensuring that PLANET4B consortium addresses all project objectives and

requirements for best practice with respect to **Equality, Diversity and Inclusion** more broadly. The Ethics Committee meet on a six-monthly basis (and ad hoc when required). It assists the Steering Committee as an internal advisory committee, helping to ensure all the agreed ethical and safety regulations are followed, and advising if they need to be updated. The PLANET4B Ethics Committee also works in close collaboration with the individual consortium partner institutions.

5.2 Humans

The PLANET4B research involves **human participants** as '**volunteers for social or human sciences research**'. The involvement of human participants refers to their role as respondents during method testing (WP2), individual case study based (WP3) and/or scaling up intervention activity (WP4), the latter including interactive and generative communication and dissemination activities.

All research undertaken in connection with the 11 case studies of the PLANET4B programme (WP3) is subject to the ethical standards in force at the respective associated lead case study partner institution, or in the case of consortium partners for whom no in-house ethical review board exists (FUG; OOF; DC; CGE; ESSRG), their involvement is subject to the ethical standards of the directly associated research partner institution (respectively: IFZ; NINA; CU; MLU) and/or CU (the latter applying in the case of ESSRG). In the event no ethical standards are yet in force at one or more institutions, the research will be subject to the ethical standards with regard to research with human participants set by the PLANET4B co-coordinating institute CU.

5.3 Procedures and criteria to identify/recruit research participants

The research involves voluntary participation of humans in the following type of individual and group research activities: serious games, story-telling workshops, in-depth, semi-structured and structured interviews/surveys; mobile (walking) interviews, discussion groups; creative visualisation workshops; face-to-face meetings; online platforms; participant observation; action research; participative methods (including participatory film making); observation of group behaviour. None of those activities belong to any of the activities highlighted by the Ethical Issues Checklist.

Participants include community members; policymakers at different administrative levels; representatives of civil society organisations; representatives of local and international businesses; and representatives of profit and non-profit organisations such as schools and social enterprises. The participants are able and are asked to give informed consent before taking part in research activities. In advance of being asked to give informed consent all participant rights as well as duties and obligations of the researchers are explained in an accompanying participant information sheet (see Annex 1). Should any case study require the recruitment of minors and/or vulnerable adults as part of the research, the PLANET4B ethics committee will support the associated partners in developing a purposefully adapted version of the participant information and informed consent sheets. These sheets will also be submitted for approval by the associated institutional ethics review board (or, where this does not exist, by CU ethics committee).

The recruitment of the participants is based on their interest or participation in community environmental activities. Participants include those who are engaged in

self-directed environmental activities, community group activities, or private and public initiatives. Others may be contacted because of the relevance of their knowledge and experience about biodiversity practice, decision-making, behaviour change and/or collaborative forms of local environmental management. The data that the participants are being asked to provide is dependent on the individual case study or type of involvement (workshop, survey) and is further elaborated in Annex 1.

Each individual consortium partner has been consulted during the drafting of V2.0 of this DMP. Furthermore, each has been tasked with identifying and communicating to the P4B-EC any/all ethical issues relating to their specific case. With regard to the identification and recruitment of research participants this includes:

- How research participants are being involved in the project, with what aim, and how they are being recruited;
- The choice of methods, e.g. serious games workshops, arts-based workshops, multi-stakeholder participation, interviews, observation, etc.;
- How respondents are informed about the collection, use, storage, sharing and ownership of the information;
- The requirement that research participants sign a letter of consent;
- An Annex with the Informed Consent Form and Information Sheet.

This information has been approved by the prevailing ethics review board at the project partner institution, or in the event of a partner not having an in-house ethics review board, it either by the directly involved research partner, or by Coventry University ethics review board. Approval has been secured prior to the commencement of any primary data collection.

5.4 Informed consent procedures

Informed consent is being secured from all human participants when they participate in any PLANET4B primary data collection activities (see Annex 1).

All participants take part in the research voluntarily and can decide at any moment to discontinue their participation. The WP3 lead, working in collaboration with the P4B-EC and the co-ordinating institutions, finalised and approved informed consent participant information sheets for all potential participants in the project (see Annex 2), providing a clear written account of the goals of the research, the methods employed and use made of its results, as well as its relevance to the respondent and the implications of participation. This document has been translated into all languages that are associated with primary data collection. The informed consent participant information sheets explain any potential risks that might be involved (for example being identified as part of a particular group or providing personal information by chance) and how confidentiality will be ensured throughout the collection, analysis and dissemination of data.

The informed consent participant information sheets also provide information on how and who to contact regarding any further questions about the project. The information is explained in person at the start of each new data collection activity, after which – unless for ethical reasons in a limited number of specific cases (e.g. blind participants) it is considered inappropriate to do so – the participants are asked to sign an informed consent form indicating their consent to participate in the research. In instances where,

either an individual indicates that they wish to participate in the study but do not want to sign any formal documentation to this effect, or it is considered inappropriate to ask them to do so (see above), they are instead asked to provide oral consent. Such oral consent is either to be given in the presence of a witness, audio recorded, or reconfirmed in writing in follow-on from the research (together with a reminder of all rights of participation (i.e. Participant information consent form))

In the case of any research activities involving minors (WP3 e.g. 'Enabling intersectional nature recreation and biodiversity stewardship for urban resilience' (Norway) case study; Environmental awareness raising in Education (Hungary) case study), adequate protection of children and young people is being ensured. All information on the research is being composed and communicated in an accessible manner and all minors are given adequate time to discuss the research with a trusted adult of their choice prior to being asked to confirm if they are willing to give informed consent for participation. In addition to securing the consent of the child, in accordance with national and institutional research ethics procedural requirements and good practice guidelines, permission is also secured from a legally recognised adult (e.g. parental consent). Where applicable any legal requirements for working with the specific population are being met in full.

All participants are informed that they can withdraw their consent for whatever reason they wish. Permission is sought to digitally record data collection activities (audio, visual), record via creative drawn image-based capture, or to record them in writing, explaining that all possible steps will be taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of participants at the level of the individual (unless participants specifically request otherwise). The researchers ensure that participants are aware of the archiving process, the accessibility of the data and asked the consent to their research material being stored in this way.

The researchers may also produce photographs, drawings, videos, or other similar forms of creative visual data, for the purpose of dissemination on-line, in conferences and exhibitions, and in publications. The use of the visual material produced as part of PLANET4B is limited to dissemination about this project and will not be used otherwise, except where explicit consent has been given by participants.

All PLANET4B beneficiaries use the standard informed consent form, translated into the relevant languages, unless host partner regulations or national laws require specific adaptations.

5.5 Templates of informed consent and information sheet

Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheet are kept on file and will be submitted upon request to the REA. Copies are included in the current version of this document (Annex 2).

5.6 Involvement of vulnerable individuals/groups and measures to prevent enhancing their vulnerability/stigmatisation

Partners have been informed about the procedures on the identification and recruitment of research participants in the specific context of vulnerable groups, as well as more broadly. The PLANET4B consortium partners ensure that all employed researchers

are trained to be sensitive to the fact that additional care is imperative when working with vulnerable people and children.

Some case studies will potentially include 'vulnerable individuals or groups'. Where applicable information on this, including the types of vulnerable individuals or groups, is included in the individual case study level DMPs (Annex 1) (together with confirmation that all associated institutional level ethical approval has been secured). Notably, participants drawn from such groups are limited either to persons able to give informed consent, or persons accompanied throughout by guardians with legal qualification to give consent on their behalf (e.g. in the case of a minor, parental consent and/or consent of a teacher (where legal authority held to do so)). Given the potential for individuals from vulnerable groups to possess lower than average educational qualifications or training means, all PLANET4B researchers are aware that it is particularly important to check whether participants need any additional support to understand the purpose of the research, data management, and particulars of consent.

5.7 Incidental findings policy

The term 'incidental findings' is used here to refer to sensitive findings which arise during the collection of research data but which do not directly relate to the aims of the study. An incidental finding could include (for example) a disclosure about criminal activity. Due to the focus of the PLANET4B research and methods of data collection (primarily qualitative; non-medical), it is anticipated that incidental findings will be unlikely to arise. In the event, however, that the PLANET4B research does produce incidental findings, the following procedure would apply. This procedure is in direct accordance with the Coventry University 'Reporting Disclosure Protocol and Guidance on Result Feedback'.

Prior to undertaking any research, individual partner institutions are required to assess the likelihood of sensitive incidental findings becoming known and document how they will be dealt with in accordance with the incidental findings policy of PLANET4B. The information sheet to be provided to research participants at the outset (in accordance with the procedure for informed consent (see below)) makes reference to the incidental findings policy to be adhered to by all PLANET4B researchers.

During data collection, in the event that an incidental finding does arise, the researcher is instructed to follow the following Coventry University protocol:

- You realise the seriousness of the information;
- End the method of data collection (dependent on the situation, either when it's safe to do so or explain why you cannot progress);
- Record any relevant notes;
- Contact the most senior level non-involved person/manager immediately or as soon as safe to do so.

In accordance with the above, the researcher is obliged to inform their line manager and/or relevant senior personnel of the occurrence and to seek immediate advice from the lead representative of the ethics research committee in their host institution. The local ethics committee (and where relevant, legal representatives within the host institution) would then inform the researcher of any statutory legal and ethical

requirement to disclose the finding to a relevant third party (for example, the police force of that nation). In parallel, the researcher is also required to inform the PLANET4B Ethics Committee of the incident. In the event that a researcher's host partner institution does not have an ethics research committee, they are required to report directly to seek advice from the PLANET4B Ethics Committee. In such a case the P4B-EC will act in accordance with the incidental findings policy of Coventry University. All incidences of incidental findings will be securely stored on file in accordance with the wider Data Management Policy of PLANET4B and made available to the REA upon request.

5.8 Securing consent/assent in the case of children and adults unable to give informed consent

PLANET4B research is limited only to persons able to give informed consent or persons accompanied throughout by guardians with legal qualification to give consent on their behalf.

5.9 Research 'in the field'

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, and the standard ethical research practice procedure of Coventry University, all researchers are required to abide by recognised procedures which are established and approved by the Steering Committee to help keep researchers and subjects safe in the field. As specified in the Horizon Europe Guidelines these include:

- Keeping careful notes of all research engagements;
- Ensuring that a designated contact person within the host institution has full details of where the researcher is, as well as expected start and completion time;
- Using mobile phones to keep in touch with the research base;
- Reporting any health and safety incidents.

Risk assessment constitutes an integral part of the ethics review process within PLANET4B. As employees, all researchers are fully insured (for working nationally and internationally) through their host partner institutions for all activities undertaken in accordance with their employment and research position (including all fieldwork activity).

5.10 Protection of Personal Data

The research involves personal data collection and processing, including 'special categories of personal data' (formally known as 'sensitive data'). The research also involves further processing of previously collected personal data (secondary use) (for further information on personal data processing, please see section on GDPR below).

The term 'data' is used here to refer to all results from research activities – varying from interview recordings and transcripts, to individual logbooks with observations and protocols, to serious games, creative workshops and other forms of participatory visual and creative data construction, to secondary data already available in the public domain.

Where personal data collection is required, it may include characteristics of gender, income, education attainment, affiliation, personal values and opinions.

In accordance with GDPR and national data protection law, where the collection of personal data is required, the PLANET4B consortium ensures that:

1. Personal data is processed fairly and lawfully.
2. Personal data is obtained only for one or more specified and lawful purposes, and is not further processed in any manner incompatible with that purpose or those purposes.
3. Personal data is adequate, relevant and not excessive in relation to the purpose or purposes for which they are processed.
4. Personal data is accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date.
5. Personal data processed for any purpose or purposes is not kept for longer than necessary for that purpose or those purposes.
6. Personal data is processed in accordance with the rights of data subjects in accordance with national data protection law.
7. Appropriate technical and organisational measures are taken against unauthorised or unlawful processing of personal data and against accidental loss or destruction of, or damage to, personal data.
8. Personal data is not transferred to a country or territory outside the European Economic Area unless that country or territory ensures an adequate level of protection for the rights and freedoms of data subjects in relation to the processing of personal data.
9. Data sharing with third parties will be limited to anonymised processed data only, with no GDPR sensitive raw data shared.

For the processing of 'special categories of personal data' (formally known as 'sensitive data') the following additional conditions will also apply:

1. The data subject has given their explicit consent to the processing of the personal data
2. Use of the data is in the substantial public interest, necessary for research purposes and neither supports measures or decisions with respect to any particular individual, nor is likely to cause substantial damage or substantial distress to any person.

5.11 Confirmation of authorisation

Where individual case studies involve the collection of personal data, prior authorisation is secured from the associated Ethics Review Committee or institutional data protection officer of the partner institution at which the researcher is employed, and/or, where required, also from the national data protection authority. Authorisation is secured in accordance with the GDPR, and with national law. Copies of the authorisation are kept on file and will be submitted upon request to the REA.

5.12 Justification of personal data collection

To be considered for approval any application for personal data collection is supported by full and detailed justification of the reason as to why collection and/or processing of personal is required. The justification is submitted to the associated ethics review committee or institutional data protection officer of the institution at which the

researcher is employed, and where required, to the national data protection authority. Copies of the justification case are kept on file and will be submitted upon request to the REA.

5.13 Templates of informed consent and information sheet

The informed consent forms and information sheet are kept on file and will be submitted upon request to the REA. Copies of both templates are included in Annex 2.

5.14 Publicly available data

Where personal data is collected and used and such data is publicly available, the researcher is required to explicitly confirm that the data were already publicly available.

5.15 Data not publicly available

Where personal data is collected and used and such data were *not* publicly available the researcher is required to secure relevant authorisation prior to its collection and use. Authorisation is to be secured in accordance with the GDPR on dataprotection, and with national law. Copies of the authorisation are kept on file and will be submitted upon request to the REA.

6 Third Countries

6.1 Conformity with Horizon 2020, European Union, national and international legislation

Of the 11 individual case studies, six involve data collection in a country outside the European Union – referred to here as a ‘third country’:

- For the case study ‘Opening nature and the outdoors to Black, Asian and ethnic minority communities’ the ‘third country’ is the UK.
- For the case studies ‘Enabling intersectional nature recreation and biodiversity stewardship for resilience’, and ‘Sustainable investment behaviour’ the ‘third country’ is Norway.
- For the case study ‘Trade and Global Value Chains’, the ‘third country’ is Brazil.
- For the case study of ‘Agriculture and Migration’, this involves research in the ‘third countries’ of UK and Switzerland. For the case study ‘Swiss attitudes towards agricultural biodiversity’ the ‘third country’ is Switzerland.

Notably, in all cases, the institution staff directly involved in undertaking data collection in the associated case study (CU – UK; NINA – Norway; FIBL – Switzerland) all already have considerable existing personal experience and knowledge of undertaking data collection in compliance with both national and European Union regulatory and ethical protocols.

6.2 Authorisation for importing of research data to the European Union

For the six case study projects involving data collection in a 'Third Country' (UK, Norway, Switzerland, Brazil), being aware and according with national and international agreement on data sharing, the following procedures are being followed:

For all case studies, where personal data needs to be transferred out of the Third Country and into the European Union, consent will first be obtained from the data subject and, where relevant in accordance with national legislation, authorisation from the relevant governing research body. The consortium partner research institution will keep on file, and submit upon request to the REA, such authorisation. In addition to gaining authorisation to export data, the consortium partner will also adhere to all aspects of the PLANET4B policy for the collection of personal data (see above).

7 Data Management and the GDPR

As of May 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation came into effect, the main principles of which (Article 5 of the GDPR) are integrated to the PLANET4B DMP as follows.

7.1 Personal data must be processed fairly and transparently

"Personal data shall be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject".

PLANET4B adheres to national and/or Coventry University strict policy on GDPR and Data Protection, which details how personal data collection should be consented, what forms and documents to use, what information is to be provided for the data subject and how the data will be secured and managed. The request also informs individuals of their rights to have data updated or removed, and the project's policies on how these rights are managed. Only relevant data is stored, whereas unused and redundant data is purged. Besides, personal data is anonymised or pseudonymised as much as possible (otherwise consented). Nonetheless there may still be occasions where we ask for further consents to use the data for open research purposes (including for instance relevant research outcome presentation, publications in journals as well as depositing a data set in an open repository). For such consent, a specific and detailed consent form will be provided.

The consortium is fully transparent in the collection of personal data. When collecting data an information leaflet and consent form includes relevant information on data use, the data collection methods and processes, the purpose of the research and the way of dissemination as well as open access (see annex 2). The data subjects are informed about the possibility to withdraw their data, as well as their rights on requesting information on the types of data stored about them.

7.2 Personal data can only be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes

"Personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes".

PLANET4B will not store any (personal) data that is not within the scope of our project.

7.3 Personal data must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for processing

“Personal data shall be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”.

Only data relevant to the project’s research is collected. Nevertheless, it may have occurred that during the data collection, additional personal information is shared that was not intended to be collected by the project. In such case, data is either be purged, or if somehow relevant to the research, anonymised and after adequate consent further processed.

7.4 Personal data must be accurate and kept up to date

“Personal data shall be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date”.

Wherever possible, all data collected will be reviewed and kept up-to-date. In cases where the datasets are difficult to keep up to date, anonymisation and relevant processing of data will be opted for. In addition, datasets will be processed as accurately as possible, with the use of indicating parameters that help with accurate data (e.g. marking the relevant year in datasets).

7.5 Personal data must be kept in a form such that the data subject can be identified only as long as it is necessary for processing

“Personal data shall be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed”.

All personal data that are no longer in use for specific research purpose will be purged as soon as they are not needed. Accordingly, also all personal data will be made anonymous once data has been processed, while it will be ensured during anonymisation that no individual can be identified (otherwise consented). At the end of the project, the anonymised data sets will be stored in open repositories. If data cannot be made anonymous, it will be pseudonymised as much as possible and stored according to project and institutional guidance archiving rules and data policy.

7.6 Personal data must be processed in a manner that ensures its security

“Personal data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures”.

All personal data are handled in accordance with relevant security protocols. Accordingly, personal data are only stored on a secure institutional server (e.g. Microsoft Teams hosted by Coventry University, or similar server by other host institutions) complying with GDPR and additional data protection, where access (via Multi Factor Authentication) is managed by the project manager and university IT

expert and only provided to authorised personnel and the partners of the project. Access can be limited and withdrawn immediately if needed. Additional people do not have access to these data. At the Microsoft Teams site, the only personal data stored and shared, will be that which a priori were consented by the data subject. Such data are forbidden to be downloaded or stored in a non-secure place. Personal data are only stored for project reporting purposes, and will be deleted as soon as they become unnecessary. Personal data will not be otherwise shared apart from via the Microsoft Teams server.

7.7 The controller's responsibility

“The controller is responsible for, and must be able to demonstrate, compliance with the Data Protection Principles and for securing the same assurances from any 3rd parties”

At project level, the project management and coordination team is responsible for the correct data management within the project, which is regularly checked. At each host institution, there will be one designated person responsible for data management and sharing, who will be accountable for managing and securing personal data sets. Besides, all members of PLANET4B liaise with relevant bodies of data management and ethical committees in terms of complying with the GDPR and additional data privacy and protection regulations.

Annex 1

Case Study Level Data Management Plans

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Urban Youth & Climate Change, Germany (CGE/MLU)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

The case study in Germany will explore a) to what extent young people, including those with less privilege, are and feel empowered to influence biodiversity and nature prioritisation in decision making; and, b) if and how various intervention methods, including experiential learning and behavioural games, as well as creative and deliberative interventions, can have empowering effects to allow them to improve biodiversity decision making. There are two guiding questions for the case study:

- 1) To what extent do young people, including those with less privilege, consider biodiversity and feel empowered to influence biodiversity and nature prioritisation in decision making?
- 2) To what extent can various intervention methods, including experiential learning and behavioural games, as well as creative and deliberative interventions, have empowering effects on younger age groups?

Data will be collected through learning community workshop reports, debriefing notes, interviews and surveys to provide responses to these questions.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

The Urban Youth case aims to deploy a range of methods to reach the behavioural change intended, such as:

- Arts-based, creative & deliberative interventions: Hike/Night Hike, Movie Screenings/Outdoor Cinema (followed by debriefing and data collected through that)
- Experiential games: Biodiversity-Food-Governance Game (followed by debriefing and data collected through that)
- Attention and framing experiments: An experiment with supermarket carts (tbc) (followed by surveys)
- Learning community workshop reports
- Understanding the overall impacts of the interventions and learning community (through semi-structured interviews)

These interventions primarily target the reflexivity aspect by fostering a connectedness with nature, encouraging environmental identity, and preparing individuals for pro-environmental behaviour. The experiential games aim at decision-making experiences, reflection, and developing a sense of capacity to contribute towards environmental

sustainability. Framing and nudging techniques are intended to trigger social norms and encourage pro-biodiversity behaviour changes in others while facilitating learning in the LC members involved in co-designing the content.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

Data will contribute to the understanding of youth views of biodiversity and their empowerment in decision-making and how interventions impact these aspects. Therefore, data will aid decision-makers, researchers and NGOs.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the PLANET4B (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload into Zenodo.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed at the project level and recommended for use by all partners, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant. Data will also be openly available via PLANET4B's website and will be published as annex in the open-access deliverables.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSST](#)). Files can be found via PLANET4B's website and in Zenodo using relevant keywords along with CORDIS.

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) will be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary in order to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated' it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

Data collected through surveys, workshops, interviews, debriefings will be stored at password protected computers; data used in deliverables and publications, including samples of questionnaires, interview questions, field notes, original tangible data (photographs/diagrams of discussion), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets are stored password protected computers; any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Confirming secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records of sensitive/personal data (if any) will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

Sensitive data embrace personal contact information (name, affiliation, email; some phone numbers), which are all stored in safe password-protected folders only accessible for project team members, and only used for the PLANET4B project. Hard copies containing sensitive information (informed consent sheets, signed participants lists) are stored in a locked cabinet at the project offices at CGE and MLU respectively. Audio files on recording facilities are deleted immediately after their transfer to the CGE or MLU server. Sensitive information about practices gained through interviews is only accessible to the team members analysing the content through personal login and password.

4. Ethical aspects

Ethical approval (not numbered) was secured from MLU's Ethical Review Commission on 10 August 2023 and from the the German Association for Experimental Economics Research with an institutional review board certificate (No. Yuh2H9y1) received on the 21st of July 2023.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Opening nature to Black, Asian and ethnic minority groups, United Kingdom (DC/CU)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

The case study aims to explore and better understand the diverse lenses through which people of colour engage with, talk about and act on the biodiversity agenda in its broadest sense. One of the goals is to promote intercultural and intra-cultural nature dialogues that brings ethnic minority communities and CU's research team together to exchange knowledge about biodiversity and create a space in which different forms of knowledge are explored. Key questions may include:

1. How is the word 'biodiversity' understood?
2. Do you see its importance/relevance to your life?
3. What do you see as potential challenges of learning about and engaging with biodiversity for yourself, or the people you interact with?
4. How do you think you could make changes to this global agenda?
5. If you could learn more, what form would that learning take?

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

The case study is centred around the establishment of a Learning Community (LC), with the LC constituting a research intervention. The research team will use a range of creative, arts- and dialogue-based methods to engage with the LC members and deliver a series of LC workshops. Notably, the co-creative intervention work undertaken with the LC will include a participatory film.

The LC comprises a group of 11 people who are attending both in-person and online workshops, which are/will take place in various natural and built environments. Additionally, each participant will have two one-to-one semi-structured interviews. The LC workshops are designed to encourage the use of creative methods to capture participants' biodiversity stories and enable the research team to collect a range of data. DC/CU have also created a WhatsApp group for the Learning Community to engage with participants throughout the project. This group will help collect participants' everyday biodiversity stories and reflections. Using this method, people can share their experiences (using a range of digital mediums) in context, and diverse (dis)engagements with biodiversity outside of formal meetings.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The data will be informative for a range of stakeholder groups, including members of civil society (especially Black, Asian and ethnic minority individuals/groups), NGOs engaging with issues of biodiversity, access to green space/countryside, health and wellbeing, rural racism (including especially those doing so from the starting point of marginalised voices, plurality and inclusivity) and policy decision makers (including

especially those with responsibility for biodiversity, sustainable development, health & wellbeing, diversity and inclusion).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload into the designated institutional repository, national archive, or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes ‘outdated’ it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) interview questions, field notes, original tangible data (audio-recordings, photographs, digital media, case study workshop reports, interview transcripts, workshop notes, system mapping data), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

All sensitive data will be stored on a centralised system (as previously detailed), which is password protected and accessible solely by relevant members of the research team. Transfer of sensitive data will be restricted to between the two PLANET4B Partners directly associated with this case study only: CU and DC.

4. Ethical aspects

An application for ethical approval was submitted by Prof Alex Franklin on 08.06.23 to Coventry University. Ethical approval was granted on 17.06.23. Ethical approval project reference number: P160041.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Agro-biodiversity management, Hungary (ESSRG)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

There is a gender division of labour in the management of plants and animals in all societies. Many times, research programs connected to plant genetic resources (PGRs) focus on crop production and usually on market-oriented crops. This way, the 'reproductive' side of farm households and gardening falls beyond the scope of research. In addition, home gardening and the collection of wild plants is usually not considered as a part of the management of PGRs. But the reproductive tasks on a farm, like seed saving, and the maintenance of heirloom varieties and landraces and experimenting with new varieties – or even species – can also be an integral part of small-scale and subsistence farming. In this case study, we want to examine the connection between gender and these reproductive tasks, especially seed saving and the management of agrobiodiversity.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

Primary data in the form of semi-structured expert interviews; Secondary qualitative data based on the analysis of interviews (which may include primary data in the form of citations); secondary, desk-based policy analysis; secondary, review of the extant literature.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

Researchers; policy decision makers with a remit for agriculture, climate change and/or environment.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload in to the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc.) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated' it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) questionnaires, interview questions, field notes, original tangible data (audio-recordings, photographs, etc.), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Confirming secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

No transfer of sensitive data is envisaged.

4. Ethical aspects

An ethical approval* was received from Coventry University before data collection started, under project reference number P161616. [*non-legally binding due to ESSRG being an organisation external to Coventry University, but in accordance with Grant Agreement Description of Action, providing formal confirmation that the proposed research adheres to the ethical standards stated meet those of Coventry University].

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Environmental awareness in education, Hungary (ESSRG)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

Through this case study ESSRG will map the institutional landscape and analyse why there is a (lack of) emphasis on the environmental crisis in schools, and how far individual scientific subjects (either as curricular or offered as extracurricular activities) can support awareness raising and facilitate a stronger connectedness to nature.

Currently, the situation of the public education system and sustainability in Hungary precarious. These areas are not a national priority, especially under the current government. However, there are several best practices for more biodiversity-inclusive education by NGOs and specific schools. Therefore, the main question for this case study is: Can biodiversity education influence a transformative change?

Through this case study we are exploring the potential of experiential learning methods – school garden, participatory theatre, game experiment – and measuring their impact on environmental relatedness.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

The following methods have been or will be used:

- Desk research and literature review with a focus on best practice case studies (already accomplished);
- Key informant interviews (semi-structured) with teachers and environmental education experts (16 interviews already carried out, some more interviews will follow later this year);
- Deliberative methods applied in selected schools as intervention methods, including: participant observation, photovoice, participatory theatre play, and a survey (in progress in two schools, and will be applied in two other school in the autumn 2024);
- Debriefing – students who participated in the intervention methods will be engaged in a short debriefing discussion (early summer and late autumn 2024). We will use visual cards (mood cards) to help them reflect on their experiences. We will observe the discussion and take notes without linking the data to specific individuals.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

- Participating students will learn about biodiversity and will have the chance to improve their relatedness to nature.
- Participating teachers will learn new approaches and experiential learning tools to teach biodiversity.
- Environmental education experts (incl. NGOs and other network organisations) will receive research results on the measurable impacts of school gardens and

other experiential learning approaches, as well as the methodological lessons learnt on how impacts at individual and community (school) level can be measured.

- The data will inform education policy- and decisionmakers (especially regarding how transformation at school and wider level is possible).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload into the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Naming conventions

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language

Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSST](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes ‘outdated’ it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) questionnaires, interview questions, field notes, interview transcripts, workshop summaries, original tangible data (audio-recordings, photographs, etc), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Confirming secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of [sensitive data](#)

Sensitive data include only the personal contact information of key informants. These data are accessible only to the field researchers and will not be shared with other consortium members or actors beyond the consortium.

4. Ethical aspects

An ethical approval* was received from Coventry University before data collection started, under project reference number P161616. [*non-legally binding due to ESSRG being an organisation external to Coventry University, but in accordance with Grant Agreement Description of Action, providing formal confirmation that the proposed research adheres to the ethical standards stated meet those of Coventry University].

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Agriculture and migration in the EU (FiBL)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

So far, very little is known about the relationship between labour availability and biodiversity conservation in agricultural landscapes, and even less on the relationship between migrant labour and biodiversity conservation. In this study, we will investigate how migrant labour influences farming systems in host and home countries, specifically regarding biodiversity-friendly practices on farm and within landscapes. We aim at finding answers for two research questions: 1) How do farms decide how to deal with labour shortage? (replacing labour-intensive practices with agrochemical alternatives, investing in mechanisation options, completely transforming the farming system, etc.); And 2) What are the effects of these alternatives on biodiversity in agricultural landscapes? (negative effects of agrochemicals, simplification of production systems due to machines or transformation of farms, extensification, etc.).

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

We collect two types of primary, qualitative data. First, we collect audio recordings and transcripts from interviews with experts, farmers, and farm workers as well as from workshops with experts and diverse stakeholders. Second, we collect expert and stakeholder inputs in matrices (in system analysis workshops) and or based on a pre-defined methodology (T3.2 workshops).

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The collected data may be of interest to local, national, and EU policy makers, NGOs with an interest in migration and/or biodiversity, and farmers who wish to produce under conditions of social sustainability.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion). Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload to the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Naming conventions

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. This applies only if data can be sufficiently anonymised to be in compliance with IPR, GDPR, or other rights and may thus be restricted.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated' it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) interview questions, field notes, original tangible data (audio-recordings, photographs, etc), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave, or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

Sensitive data will not be transferred.

4. Ethical aspects

Ethical approval for the research within this case study was obtained prior to the start of the data collection. It was issued by the Ethics Committee of FiBL's department of Food System Sciences under the number FSS-2023-005.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Agro-biodiversity and religion, Switzerland (FiBL)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

Agriculture is one of the major drivers behind land use change and biodiversity loss. There's some consensus that individual values are one of the key determinants of environmental behaviour. But where do these values come from? For many people, they use religion or a value-based system of beliefs to calibrate their moral compass. While the relationship between gender and pro-biodiversity farming is already studied, less is known about the relationship between religion and biodiversity decisions. Switzerland is predominantly Christian, with catholic and protestant the dominant doctrines, depending on the region. This case aims to explore how a farmer's religion or value-based system of beliefs interacts with their farming and environmental behaviour. The main research questions are:

1. In what ways are farmers influenced by their religious belief?
2. What assumptions are being made by policymakers and what interpretations are farmers drawing from policies with religious beliefs?

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

Qualitative data has been collected using audio-recordings of interviews with farmers and a focus group discussion with the learning community members. The anonymised audio data is transcribed electronically. Farmers also share pictures or the researcher takes pictures and/or videos of items or activities that farmers share. These are stored as visual data. Furthermore, an online survey is planned to be administered.

1.3 Data utility

The collected data may be of interest to local, national, and EU policy makers, religious institutions and NGOs with an interest in eco-theology and/or biodiversity.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload to the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Naming conventions

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated' it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) questionnaires, interview questions and responses, field notes, original tangible data like photographs, analysed data, coding steps.

(b) Secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

All data published will be anonymised with sensitive identifiable information removed from the published data. Survey data will be collated and presented collectively. In the event that participant's narratives are used or exact words are used, all identifiable information will be removed or pseudonymised to retain meaning of statements. No sensitive data will therefore be transferred.

4. Ethical aspects

Ethical approval for the research within this case study was obtained prior to the start of the data collection. It was issued by the Ethics Committee of FiBL's department of Food System Sciences under the number FSS-2023-005.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Biodiverse Edible City Graz, Austria (IFZ/FUG)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

The Graz-based case study will explore how biodiversity and social justice aspects could be taken more into account in the planning and realisation of urban green spaces and the food provision strategy of the city of Graz.

The research work tackles two for a, where relevant activities and decision-making processes take place:

(1) One concerns the practices and formalities of setting up and implementing strategies in the City of Graz. Related data are collected within the “policy LC”, which comprises representatives from the municipality and various stakeholder groups. This LC is dedicated to governance issues around integrated policy and decision-making. The overall process started with individual (interviews) and joint (workshops) reflections on the status quo and actual practices. The next steps will then aim at awareness raising for the relevance and potential benefits of trans-sectorial and participatory planning processes, and finally conclude with recommendations on how integrated processes, which consider more biodiversity and a socially just urban foodscape, can be fostered in future. (2) The second set of data is generated within the “citizen LC”, which engages 15 women, who are affected by intersectionality aspects. This LC is guided through a process of setting up a community garden and the planning of a bigger green plot, which is supposed to become an Edible Park within the next years. The implemented activities aim at awareness raising, knowledge co-creation and capacity building, which should help members to reflect and make sense of establishing links between biodiversity, food and urban green spaces. Finally, the overall process should empower them to participate in related planning (and eventually also implementation) activities and generate learnings about how to foster less privileged citizens’ agency.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

Desk research (ongoing):

- Review of literature (intersectionality; integrated policy approaches; good practice examples).
- Review of relevant policy documents (national and local level).

Policy LC:

- Personal data: names, affiliation, email (storage in protected area on IFZ server; not disclosed to others beyond the IFZ-project team).
- Pictures from various intervention activities (individual consent provided for each activity).
- Data of ‘Future Walk’ and Kick-off event: protocol of content.

- Semi-structured interviews (14) with key stakeholders and municipality representatives on actual practices: audios nor transcripts (will not be made available as we guaranteed interview partners anonymity).
- System mapping: drawings and protocols.
- Community mapping: drawings, maps, protocols.

Citizen LC:

- Personal data: names, affiliation, email and/or phone numbers (storage in protected area on FUG server; not disclosed to others beyond the FUG project team).
- Questionnaire to LC participants (anonymised – personal data are with FUG, the questionnaire will be implemented by IFZ): socio-demographic data (age, gender, religion, profession, education, family status, income, housing situation, care duties).
- Pictures from various intervention activities (individual consent provided for each activity).
- Data from various intervention activities:
 - Audio files & transcripts
 - Notes from participatory observation
 - Pictures for Topothek (artist project)
 - Community mapping: drawings, maps, protocols
 - Food stories
 - (ev. Video files produced by participants)
 - Science education workshops: debriefing notes

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

As the Graz-based case represents a Living Lab, which also needs to grant 'safe spaces' for sensible information, reflection and interaction, neither personal data nor audio files and transcripts will be made openly accessible. Other data as listed above may be of interest for a range of target groups, which are dealing with topics/issues around biodiversity, urban planning & green spaces, social justice, gender & intersectionality, participatory governance, urban food strategies, and health & wellbeing. This applies to researchers, students, people from policy & administration, NGOs/CSOs, educational institutions and community centres.

Beyond the data listed above, we will also make information and protocols for the design of the intervention activities available. This might be of specific interest for peers, who plan and practically implement similar intervention activities.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling

process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload in to the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Personal and sensitive data related to the research participants will be kept closed, in compliance with the GDPR. Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (specific context within a specific city). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable the completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research

participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated' it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) questionnaires, interview questions, field notes, original tangible data (audio-recordings, photographs, etc), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Confirming secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records are kept in a lockable cabinet at the IFZ office (Schlögelgasse 2) with controlled access: the keys are with the institute's secretary (Franziska Häller) and the head of the institute (Jürgen Suschek-Berger).

All electronic data and records are stored on the password-protected IFZ server (personal login and password). Access to PLANET4B-related folders is only granted to project team members. Access is updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software are not left logged in and unattended.

The transcription of audio files is done by an IFZ team member, who signed a confidentiality agreement.

Personal data for the citizen LC are stored in encrypted containers on the password-protected server of FUG, and can only be accessed by the management board and the two team members who facilitate the citizen LC.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. Cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records is not used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks are not used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

Sensitive data embrace personal contact information (name, affiliation, email; some phone numbers), which are all stored in safe password-protected folders only

accessible for project team members, and only used for the PLANET4B project. Hard copies containing sensitive information (informed consent sheets, signed participants lists) are stored in a locked cabinet at the IFZ office. Audio files on recording facilities are deleted immediately after their transfer to the IFZ server. The sociodemographic data of the citizen LC are fully anonymised and stored in password-protected folders on the IFZ server, while the personal data of this LC is on the password-protected server of FUG (no access for IFZ-team members!).

Sensitive information about policy practices gained through interviews is only accessible to the team members analysing the content through personal login and password.

4. Ethical aspects

The ethical approval for undertaking the research was secured prior to the commencement of data collection by the data protection coordinator and the ethics board of IFZ.

5. Other

As already addressed above, the research design of a Living Lab requires the creation of safe spaces, where participants can openly speak and critically reflect. Therefore the informed consent implies the concession that neither the audio files nor the transcripts will be shared with third parties beyond those team members, who implement and analyse the collected data. This also implies a pseudonymisation of participants affiliation and function. This was particularly relevant for municipality members.

Informed consent is collected for every activity separately.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Nature Recreation, Oslo, Norway (NINA/OOF)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

The Norwegian intensive case study targets better access to outdoor recreation and nature experiences for youth with disabilities by creating more inclusive (social or physical) environments, in ways that are also beneficial for biodiversity. Experiences from disabled persons, parents, and organisations working at the intersection between nature recreation and inclusion are collected and analysed. The case also comprises a pilot and/or a participant observation study, with the direct involvement of underprivileged groups such as children with disabilities and organisations. The goal is to identify paths for more inclusive outdoor recreation activities that also highlight the importance and contribute to the preservation of biodiversity.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

This case study and related interventions have been planned in four stages:

- 1st stage: Survey with parents of children with disabilities' use of biodiversity and natural/outdoors areas (completed). The questions about disability were integrated into a broader, nationwide NINA-survey on children's outdoor activities and use of nature in general. The survey was conducted under another NINA-project, in compliance with GDPR and the Norwegian data protection law.
- 2nd stage: Learning about challenges/possibilities for interventions: Mapping of organisations involved. Establishment of learning community in collaboration with Oslo Recreational Council, consisting of youth with disabilities that are part of a mentoring program, parents of youth with disabilities, and representatives from outdoor recreation organisations (ongoing – ethical approval and informed consent obtained). Qualitative interviews with representatives from outdoor recreation organisations (completed – ethical approval and informed consent obtained).
- 3rd stage: Pilot/observation of already existent activities (planned). Possible activities: observe outdoor recreation activities involving youth with disabilities, ask the youth to take photos of nature, identifying which elements are important for them, etc. No registration or collection of personal data. According to Norwegian law, ethical approval and informed consent is therefore not required. Informed consent will nevertheless be obtained, in a format suitable for the target group.
- 4th stage: Research-based discussions, synthesising facts/case outcomes.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The data will be useful to youth with disabilities, their families, researchers, planners, outdoor recreation organisations, and policy makers. It will identify key barriers and facilitators to improving access to nature experiences for disabled youth. Highlighting these factors emphasises the importance of conserving nature and biodiversity for the social inclusion of disadvantaged groups.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload into the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Naming conventions

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes ‘outdated’ it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Anonymous survey data (2) Contact information (names, telephone numbers and/or email addresses to members of learning community and interview informants), (3) Informed consent with signatures (4) Notes from workshops with learning community (5) Audio-recordings of interviews, (6) Transcriptions of interviews (7) Field notes (8) Photos taken by youth with disabilities during activities.

(b) Secure storage of data:

(1) Anonymous survey data are stored on NINA’s encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication. (2) Contact information (names, telephone numbers and/or email addresses to members of learning community and interview informants) are stored on NINA’s encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication *separately from all other data*. (3) Informed consent sheets with signatures are kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. (4) Notes from workshops with learning community are anonymised continuously, before they are stored on NINA's encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication. (5) Audio-recordings of interviews are stored on NINA’s encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication. The recordings will be deleted at the end of the projects (no later than 01.03.2026). (6) Transcriptions of

interviews are stored on NINA's encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication. They will be anonymised (all direct identifiers removed) no later than 01.03.2026. (7) Field notes will be anonymised before they are stored on NINA's encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication. The tangible notes will be destructed. (8) Photos taken by youth with disabilities during activities will be stored on NINA's encrypted server with access restriction and multi-factor authentication. The photos will be manipulated to remove persons or object that may lead to direct identification.

Access to the data stored on NINA's server is only possible by using personal login and password. Passwords for accessing the data will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

The interviews were recorded on a digital recorder. The recordings were then quickly transferred to NINA's encrypted server and deleted from the recorder. Although OOF has participated in workshops and interviews, as well as the recruitment of informants and learning community members, this has always been under the supervision of involved NINA researchers. One of the employees of OOF is now pursuing a master's degree using data from the project. Therefore, the person currently has a dual connection to NINA and OOF and has access to a desk at NINA's office in Oslo, where he can directly access and work with the data on NINA's encrypted server. He has also been responsible for transcribing the interviews, which took place in NINA's office. This arrangement ensures that there is no transfer of data between OOF and NINA, since all data are securely stored on NINA's server. Learning community workshops have been held at NINA's office in Oslo, ensuring that notes taken during the workshops and tangible informed consent sheets have never left the restricted-access building. Notes from the planned pilots/activities will be directly anonymised, avoiding the registration of any information that may lead to direct identification and using pseudonyms. Any photos taken by disabled youth will be transferred as quickly as possible to NINA's encrypted server. We aim to use disposable cameras; in which case, the cameras will be destroyed immediately afterward. If any small storage units, such as USB memory sticks, are used for the transfer of photos, the devices will be encrypted.

4. Ethical aspects

Prior to data collection, the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (SIKT) evaluated and approved that the Norwegian intensive case study complies with data protection legislation and gaining lawful access to personal data. SIKT-reference number: 835768.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Sustainable Investment Behaviour, Global-EU-Norway (NINA)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

The case study investigates the impact of cognitive biases on sustainable investment behaviour, especially amidst the complexities of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) uncertainties. Employing a systematic literature review and semi-structured interviews with stakeholder board members, the study will provide an understanding of how various biases influence decision-making in the realm of sustainable investing practices.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

The analysis will utilise a combination of systematic literature reviews, semi-structured interviews, and desk-based research. This comprehensive approach aims to triangulate data from multiple sources, providing a robust foundation for understanding the influence of cognitive biases on sustainable investment decisions amidst ESG uncertainties.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

This analysis aims to offer valuable insights for researchers and companies relying on ESG scores in their analyses, providing an opportunity to enhance internal policies to mitigate biases in investment decisions. Additionally, it may prove instrumental for companies involved in shaping ESG standards, improving the credibility of ESG scores, particularly in areas like biodiversity, and fostering more informed and responsible investment practices.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion). Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload to the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed. A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary in order to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated' it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

- (1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) questionnaires, field notes.
- (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

Given our focus on literature review and semi-structured interviews, we do not anticipate any sensitive data transfer. To uphold confidentiality, all interview outputs will undergo pseudonymisation, ensuring that participants' identities are protected while maintaining the integrity of the data and inputs collected.

4. Ethical aspects

Stakeholder board meetings employed a deliberative group discussion approach, with prior consent obtained for recording the sessions. Consequently, there was no necessity for Shared Services in Education and Research (SIKT) permission.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: Trade and global value chains (soya/beef), Brazil, Netherlands/EU (RU)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

This case investigates the consequences of new public EU regulations on sustainable supply chains. Although the case focuses on the EU Regulation on Deforestation-free Products (EUDR), other policies, such as the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD) can be included in the analysis. The case aims to analyse how such EU policies will impact socio-biodiversity loss linked to international commodity trade of soy and beef between Brazil and Europe and, more specifically, the Netherlands. In line with this, the case has two learning objectives:

- Firstly, to understand the potential and limitations of recent European Union supply chain policies, for example the EUDR (European Union Deforestation Regulation) and the CSDDD (Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive), to curb deforestation and biodiversity loss in Brazil and the Netherlands, as well as the interplay between EU policies and relevant national policies in Brazil and the Netherlands.
- Secondly, to identify and analyse distinct socio-biodiversity challenges and risks (for biodiversity and people, considering intersectionality) connected to the soy and the beef supply chains in Brazil's Cerrado and Amazon biomes (supply side) and in the Netherlands (demand side).

For now, our data collection is being implemented through a) literature review of relevant scientific references and gray literature (policy reports, NGO reports, companies' sustainability reports); b) semi-structured interviews.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

Primary data: our primary dataset includes transcripts of original semi-structured interviews, as well as the related data analysis materials (Excel and Word files). Original audio-visual files of those interviewees who agreed to be recorded will also be included in the dataset. *If field research materialises*, audiovisual data collected in the field will also compose this dataset (mainly including videos, photos, and primary documents collected in loco).

Secondary data: this dataset provides a list with documents related to the supply chains investigated (e.g. companies' sustainability reports, trade balances), as well as the EU policies of interest to the case study (EUDR, CSDDD). Most likely, the format of original documents will be either PDF or Word files. The analysis of this material will be provided in the format of an Excel file.

1.3 Data utility

The main beneficiaries from the datasets generated will be researchers, NGOs and policy analysts working with topics associated with the thematic focus of this case study. Importantly, both the EUDR (entered in effect on June 2023) and the CSDDD (the EU votes on the final directive text on April 2024) are new policies. So, our databases will be an important contribution to the field, useful both to researchers and practice-oriented professionals.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Where applicable, datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload into the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed, to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary in order to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

In compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Because of the (primarily) social science nature of the data there is no time limit for its re-usability. Even if social science data becomes ‘outdated’ it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) Data used in publications, including samples of (e.g.) questionnaires, field notes, original tangible data (audio-recordings, photographs, etc), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected.

Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password. Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data.

The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will not be used as it can carry significant governance and management risks. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of [sensitive data](#)

Sensitive data procedures for sharing research data include keeping all data in the personal computers of the lead researcher (Dr. Vinícius Mendes), and in a cloud (One Drive), and only transferring documents to/from Brazil or other non-EU consortium partners in PLANET4B when strictly necessary. Additionally, every time a document is sent by email to countries within and outside the EU, the VPN of the Radboud University is previously activated, to prevent data leaking and to mitigate the risk of third parties accessing such data.

4. Ethical aspects

Ethics approval was secured on 4 August 2023, and it was issued by the Ethics Assessment Committee of the Faculty of Law and the Nijmegen School of Management (EACLM) of Radboud University, Nijmegen, Netherlands, and registered under EACLM number 2023.12.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN OF PLANET4B CASE STUDY: From 'ego-system to eco-system' in fashion, Italy (UNIFI)

1. Data summary

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation

This case study will study the connection between the Fashion Value Chain (FVC) and biodiversity loss and explore potential transformations of the sector to better prioritise biodiversity. The case will support social actors, companies and public institutions to discuss, learn and find transformative change as a mean to integrate (prioritise) biodiversity protection within socio-economic activities, such as product redesign, and transformation of different eco-social relationships with the environment. The main aim is to understand the role of biodiversity in changing the fashion industry.

1.2 Types and formats of data generated/collected

Type of data generated and collected are the following:

- Personal data (for members of the advisory Board): 1) name, 2) affiliation, 3) mailing address, 4) professional background, 5) job title, 6) gender, 7) photos and videos.
- Other data:
 - Data from on-line and in-person expert interviews (standard format e.g. m.4 audio files).
 - Data from on-line and in-person scenario workshops and other participatory activities (e.g. m4. audio files, mp4 video files, docx format).

In-person activities take place in Italy, mainly in Tuscany and Piedmont.

These types of data are qualitative and context specific and, typically, cannot be reproduced, which makes the strategies applied for documentation of this type of data very important. Therefore, a careful and elaborate preparation of the way that data will be registered (instruments, conditions and observation method) is crucial. Once this type of data is captured, all subsequent steps (coding, aggregation, processing, analysis) will be reproducible.

1.3 Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The data could be useful for researchers (i.e. studying fashion, transformative change and/or biodiversity), private companies and stakeholders from the sector (i.e. to better design their biodiversity policies and be more aware about their impacts), policymakers (i.e. to improve policy design and evaluation), and Civil Society Organisations and Environmental NGOs (i.e. to inform advocacy actions).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The metadata will consist of information that provides detailed insight into the archived data. This will include type of data, date of collection, location (country and region) of collection, category of respondent, thematic focus, keywords, sampling process/number of respondents, data collection method. Metadata will also be downloadable from a dedicated page of the [PLANET4B](#) (which will remain active for a minimum of 5 years after project completion).

2.1.2 Identifiability of data

Datasets will be assigned a DOI at the time of upload into the designated institutional repository, national archive or other open science compliant repository.

2.1.3 Outline naming conventions used

A systematic file naming convention will be developed to ensure adequate organising and retrieving of documents, as well as managing records through their lifecycle. The file naming system will build on the best practices identified by e.g. [CESSDA](#). A systematic and clear directory structure will also be developed.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Data to be made openly available

Audio files and transcripts from interviews and group discussions will not be shared via open access as a full pseudonymisation would not be possible without losing essential content (i.e. specific contextual data for the location and/or respondent). Only protocols, which can be fully pseudonymised will be made available. In the case of all other data, personal and sensitive data as well as data that cannot be anonymised sufficiently to be in compliance with GDPR will also not be made available.

2.2.2 Data availability

Data will be uploaded to [ZENODO](#), as part of a larger PLANET4B project data collection. The repository is [OpenAIRE](#) compliant.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data interoperability

Interoperability will be facilitated by providing metadata, including based on the Controlled Vocabularies proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative ([DDI](#)). Keywords will be created, including where applicable, using the European Language Social Science Thesaurus ([ELSST](#)).

2.4. Making data reusable

2.4.1 Data licencing

Depending on the data, a specific Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) may be applied for. The license [if needed] will be carefully selected, taking into

consideration Intellectual Property Rights and additional legal and ethical requirements.

2.4.2 Date of data availability

The data will be made available for public re-use during the final months (months 33–36) of the PLANET4B project. Restricting full public availability of data until then is necessary to enable completion of data collection, due processing of the data, to generate the necessary metadata and in accordance with the rights of research participants to withdraw from the study for a set period beyond their date of participation.

2.4.3 Reuse of data by third parties

The context-specific nature of the data may limit its subsequent usability by third parties. However, in compliance with Open Access, pseudonymised data (e.g. interview transcripts, etc) will be made available in support of potential re-use by third parties after the end of the project. Some restrictions may apply if IPR, GDPR or other rights demand such restriction.

2.4.4 Reuse of data by third parties

Although the context-specific nature of data limits its usability by third parties, the data's primarily social science nature allows for its continued re-usability. Even if social science data becomes 'outdated', it will continue to have potential value in perpetuity as historical data.

3. Data security

3.1 Secure storage, data recovery and transfer of sensitive data

(a) Types of data to be stored

(1) the types of data to be stored are data from e.g on-line and in-person expert interviews, data from on-line and in-person scenario workshops, focus groups and other participatory activities. They include transcription and notes, field notes, original tangible data (audio recording, photographs, video recording, etc.), analysed data, coding steps, intermediate data sets, etc. (2) Any additional data specifically required by involved beneficiaries/partners/the European Commission, including records of procedures, etc.

(b) Secure storage of data

Tangible data and paper records will be kept in lockable cabinets or offices with controlled access, when not under the direct supervision of a member of the research team. Access to electronic data and records are controlled by passwords and, where appropriate, access to individual files/databases will also be password protected. Passwords will be known only by authorised individuals. Access controls will regularly be reviewed and updated as individuals join, leave or change roles within the project. Computers and software will not be left logged in and unattended.

Personal and sensitive data will be saved on a server with restricted physical and digital access. Access to the data is only possible by using personal login and password.

Before using any storage media for electronic data and records, consideration will be given to appropriate security and back-up of the data. The use of cloud computing and software as a service provider to store research records will just be used when a data storage contract ensuring privacy, security, and backup in Italian and institutional servers exist. Small media devices such as USB sticks will not be used as the primary storage location for personal data or confidential information and will be encrypted if used to transport respondent identifiable data.

(c) Transfer of sensitive data

There will not be any transfer of sensitive data.

4. Ethical aspects

The ethical approval for undertaking the research was secured by the Bioethics committee at the University of Pisa (*Parere* 11/2024).

Annex 2

PLANET4B

ETHICS: PLANET4B Informed Consent Template Forms

Informed Consent Form for participating in the research:

‘understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making’ (PLANET4B)

Name of researcher: *[Insert name]*

Name of institution: *[Insert name]*

Name of sponsor: European Union – Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation Programme: Grant Agreement No 101082212

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- **Part I: Information Sheet** (to share information about the study with you)
- **Part II: Certificate of Consent** (for signatures if you choose to take part)

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction PLANET4B

My name is [...] and I am currently conducting a research project on “[**INSERT NAME OF CASE STUDY &/OR WP activity**]”. This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme: Grant Agreement No 101082212. This research does not reflect the opinions of the European Commission.

Before you decide to take part, it is important you understand why the research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully. You may talk about this project to anybody you feel comfortable with, and please take some time to reflect on whether you would like to participate or not. If there’s anything you don’t understand in this information sheet, feel free to ask any questions at any time.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research project aims to:

- 1) To understand how factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability, norms, values and behaviour intersect and are implicated in biodiversity relevant decision-making across a range of different scales and settings; and
- 2) To channel this understanding of complexity into the design of stakeholder interventions, transformative pathways and a series of targeted (yet, scalable) policy recommendations, in order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss.

Type of Research Intervention

The research will involve an *interview/workshop/... [insert/replace with other method if relevant]* with you. The *interview/workshop/... [insert/replace with other method if relevant]* will be recorded so that I can later analyse the information that you provide.

Participant Selection

You are invited to this research due to your experiences as a member of the *[XXX/employee of/... (INSERT/REPLACE AS APPLICABLE)]* and involvement/expertise in *[XXX/employee of/... (INSERT/REPLACE AS APPLICABLE)]*. Your experience will help me understand the *[XXX (insert as applicable)]*.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is voluntary. You can choose to participate or not. If you do decide to take part, please keep this Information Sheet and complete the Informed Consent Form to show that you understand your rights in relation to the research, and that you are happy to participate. You are free to withdraw at any stage. You do not need to give a reason. A decision to withdraw, or not to take part, will not affect you in any way.

Procedures

With your consent, the *[insert method of data collection]* will be recorded. All electronic data will be stored on a password-protected computer file at the host institution. All paper records (if relevant) will be stored in a locked filing cabinet in the same institution. Your consent information will be kept separately from your responses in order to minimise risk in the event of a data breach. The lead researcher will take responsibility for secure data storage and (if requested) pseudonymised or anonymised versions of the research findings (which may include raw data) will subsequently be uploaded on a secure open access data repository (by or before October 31st 2025) for potential access by other researchers as part of the Horizon Europe European Commission commitment to Open Science. All data management, processing and storage procedures will be conducted in full conformity with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018.

The research might potentially include sensitive issues and personal data. Personal data shall be processed fairly and lawfully. Personal data shall be obtained only for *[add a specified and lawful purpose]*, and shall not be further processed in any manner incompatible with that purpose or those purposes. There is a risk also that for any reason you might feel uncomfortable talking about some of the topics. I do not wish for

this to happen. You do not have to answer any question or take part in the research if talking about something makes you feel uncomfortable.

Duration

The *[insert method of data collection]* will last approximately *[duration]*.

Data storage

Data will be kept on the server of the institution by whom the researcher is employed *[Insert name of consortium partner institution]*. Data will also be made available in accordance with the Horizon Europe commitment to Open Access to Research Data.

Data Protection Rights

[Insert name of consortium partner institution] is a Data Controller for the information you provide. You have the right to access information held about you. Your right of access can be exercised in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2018. You also have other rights including rights of correction, erasure, objection, and data portability.

Confidentiality and legal duty of disclosure

Unless you request that we do so, your identity will not be revealed in connection with any of the outputs from this research. Although direct quotes from the research may be used in academic and policy articles, all material will be anonymised or pseudonymised. As with any research project there could be limits to confidentiality, including specifically in relation to the occurrence of sensitive incidental findings, in the event of which a legal duty of disclosure may apply to the researcher. However, this research does not deal with any sensitive subjects, so the likelihood of such experiences is very small.

Benefits and reimbursement

You will benefit from the results in the sense that the outcomes will provide insights into how to *[insert as applicable]*. They will also help to build capacities of people to engage in *[insert as applicable]* and thus strengthen connectivity between *policy-makers, academics, businesses and civil society [REVISE/REPLACE as applicable]*. There will be no reimbursement for your contribution.

Sharing the Results

The research is expected to be published in both academic journals and other public fora. The data for example will be used in policy briefs and reports, open access academic training material, academic papers, conferences and workshops and social media communication material. In addition, any fully anonymised data sets will be made available for sharing via an open access repository. Data sharing will, however, be limited to anonymised processed data only, with no raw data shared.

Who to Contact

If you have any questions about this project feel free to ask me now or later. You can contact me at *[Institution name and address + email address for researcher]*. If your questions are not answered adequately, you wish to make a complaint, or if you want to talk to somebody other than me, feel free to contact the research project co-ordinator:

Dr. Ilkhom Soliev

Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg (MLU Halle), Germany.
ilkhom.soliev@zirs.uni-halle.de

[Insert also here a name and contact email for your Institutional Data Protection Officer]

Part II: Certificate of Informed Consent Form [Example template]

'understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making' (PLANET4B)

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions

Check this box if agree

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason

Check this box if agree

3. I understand that all the information I provide will be treated in confidence and that any personal data I provide will be processed in full accordance with GDPR (2018)

Check this box if agree

4. I understand that I also have the right to change my mind about participating in the study for a short period after the study has concluded *[insert deadline here]*

Check this box if agree

5. I agree to be recorded and for anonymised quotes to be used as part of the research project

Check this box if agree

6. I agree to take part in the research project

Check this box if agree

Name of participant:

Signature of participant: Date:

[If applicable – NB. For minors consent of both parents is required] Witnessed by:

Name of witness:

Signature of witness: Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature of researcher: Date:

Annex 3

PLANET4B Website Privacy Policy

Introduction

The Privacy Policy of PLANET4B project is a document addressing you as Data Subject, i.e. the owner of your personal data. The Privacy Policy explains the collected personal data process and cookie policy of the project.

The PLANET4B project is committed to protect your personal data and to respect your privacy.

Type of data and related treatment

1.1 Data voluntarily provided by the Subscriber

The explicit and voluntary provision of personal data provided by the data owner is essential in order to have access to certain services offered by the Data Controller through the website (e.g. Newsletter Subscription) and to receive the requested update. This involves the collection of personal data and contact details, as well as any other personal data that are required to respond to requests or to provide the available services. The PLANET4B consortia doesn't collect nor treat sensitive data.

Navigation Data (Data deriving from User's navigation)

During routine activities, the computer system may store some of your browsing data. These data, although not collected in order to be associated with your identity, may allow indirect recognition of your identity when processing and associating with the data held by the Data Controller. For this reason, they could be considered "personal data" according to the Privacy Regulation. This category of data (which includes, by way of example but not limited to, IP addresses and domain names of the User's computer) is collected by the Data Controller for statistical purposes in anonymous form, but by means of some data processing procedures it could be possible to trace the User identity in order to ascertain any liability for crimes committed via the Website or damages against it.

Purpose of data collection and treatment

The personal data serve the following communication and dissemination activities of the PLANET4B project:

- To provide information and answers about project activities, research results and content from the projects we work on;
- To carry out statistics and reports in anonymous form (e.g. assessment the download of the material provided, the number of times a website was accessed, the most visited pages, the average visit duration, the country of origin of Users, etc.).

We commit to ensure that Subscribers will always be free to opt-out and exercise their rights as regard to the treatments mentioned above. Each communication has an opt-out link where you can inform us about your decisions.

Data Controller

GoodIssue Ltd./Jóügy Kft. the beneficiary partner and lead of communication and dissemination work package is the Data Controller of the personal data collected and treated via PLANET4B website.

GoodIssue Ltd. management has the accountability and the responsibility to set structure and procedures to treat and protect your data. Appointed members of the staff are responsible for the actual treatment of your data. Other consortium's members might occasionally operate as Data Processor, in that case, they will comply with the same rules as stated in this privacy notice.

Data protection and storage

The data processing related to the website's services takes place at the registered office of Jóügy Kft, Budapest Lehel u. 15. H-1115.

4 Cookies Policy

Our websites use cookies so that we can provide you with the best possible user experience.

Without some of these cookies, the website simply would not work. Other cookies perform functions like recognising you each time you visit the site or helping our team to understand which parts of the site you find most interesting and useful.

Cookies used on PLANET4B website:

- Session cookie – A session cookie only lasts for the duration of the user's website visit. A web browser normally deletes session cookies when it quits.
- Persistent cookie – A persistent cookie will outlast user sessions. If a persistent cookie has its maximum age set to 1 year, then, within the year, the initial value set in that cookie would be sent back to the server every time the user visited the server. This could be used to record a piece of information such as how the user initially came to this website.
- Secure cookie – A secure cookie is only used when a browser is visiting a server via HTTPS, ensuring that the cookie is always encrypted when transmitting from client to server.
- First-party cookie – First-party cookies are cookies set with the same domain (or its subdomain) in the browser's address bar.
- Third-party cookie – Third-party cookies are cookies set with different domains from the one shown on the address bar (i.e. the web pages on that domain may feature content from a third-party domain – e.g. Google Maps or YouTube). Privacy setting options in most modern browsers allow you to block third-party tracking cookies.

Legislation of personal data protection and treatment

The Data Controller has the Legitimate Interest to treat your personal data as per art. 6 (f) GDPR 179/2016. Our detailed rationale for claiming legitimate interest is based on a Legitimate Interest Assessment (LIA), periodically reviewed. We believe that it is a mutual benefit to remain in contact; you will receive from us communications

exclusively as detailed in the previous paragraphs. We are counting to hear from you back on the specific topics through our communication activity for a mutual growth.

Duration of data process

Your data will be processed for the whole duration of the mandatory maintenance of the project website and results or until the date when Data Subject withdraws its consent to data process.

Data transfer

Data Controller processes do not require any transfer of data to external third parties with the sole exception of auditing authorities of the public institutions that funded the project. Following the processes and treatments described above, your personal data can be communicated to the Data Controller's staff. Furthermore, and in so far as necessary, Personal data shall be disclosed, in so far as they are concerned, to but not limited to the following categories:

- Organisations that are part of the PLANET4B Consortium;
- Persons in charge of managing the website and the related activities;
- Persons who provide services for the management of the information system of the company;
- Persons carrying out monitoring, auditing and certification activities linked to the project;

The personal data you provide will not be sold to or shared with third parties.

Rights of Data Subject

EU GDPR legislation guarantees the right to access, rectify or erase your personal data and the right to restrict the processing of your personal data. Where applicable, you also have the right to object to the processing of your personal data and the right to data portability. To read more about the rights of data subjects and the rights and obligations of data controllers see here: [General Data Protection Regulation \(2018\)](#).

You have consented to provide your personal data for the present processing operation. You can withdraw your consent at any time by notifying the Data Controller.

The withdrawal will not affect the lawfulness of the processing carried out before you have withdrawn the consent.

You can exercise your rights by contacting the Data Controller.

Your requests will be handled within a maximum of 10 working days.

Contact information: iroda@jougykft.hu

Changes to Privacy Notice

If necessary, we may amend or update this Privacy Statement to reflect changes on the website and feedback from our users. If there are material changes in the way we use or process your personal data, we will notify you by posting a notice of the changes before these come into effect or by sending a notification to you directly.